

1 **Control of UBE2N by HPV E6.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described
7 functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We
8 demonstrate here control of *Ube2n* by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV E6 across type: for
9 both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

10 Citations

11 1. Barreyro, L., Sampson, A.M., Ishikawa, C., Hueneman, K.M., Choi, K., Pujato, M.A.,
12 Chutipongtanate, S., Wyder, M., Haffey, W.D., O'Brien, E. and Wunderlich, M., 2022. Blocking UBE2N
13 abrogates oncogenic immune signaling in acute myeloid leukemia. *Science translational medicine*,
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